

Novel robotic platform for Ultrasound-guided Intravascular Catheterization

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Abstract—Intravascular catheterization is typically performed by manual insertion and implies radiation exposure for both the patient and the surgeon. The transition to an intrinsically safe and cost-effective imaging technique, as ultrasound, is hampered by technological limitations, as low resolution and limited field of view hindering clear and complete anatomical vision. Taking advantage from robotics and machine learning (ML), this paper presents a robotic ultrasound (RUS) platform to remove radiation exposure and automatize the procedure. To this purpose, 3D vascular reconstruction is carried out with sub-millimetric precision thanks to robotic probe manipulation and deep learning-based image segmentation. ML is also considered to supervise automatic catheter insertion by using a logistic regressor classifier. This is able to determine the presence of the catheter tip with sensitivity and specificity equal to 98%. Such feedback is exploited to close the loop of a variable structure binary feedback control module for automatic catheter manipulation with a control error of 3.3 mm.

Keywords—Robotic Ultrasound, Machine Learning, Vascular Reconstruction, Ultrasound Imaging

I. INTRODUCTION

Ultrasound (US) is among the preferred medical imaging techniques thanks to its low-cost, real-time performance and non-ionizing nature. However, its limited spatial resolution and the presence of artifacts and noise make image understanding a complex task. Deep learning (DL) strategies proved effective in reducing clinicians burden by facilitating medical image analysis [1, 2]. Nevertheless, US images quality, thus DL methods performance, depends on operator's probe handling abilities. Robots can support image acquisition standardization [3] and favor reliable 3D volume reconstruction from the sequence of 2D images [4]. Indeed, robotic arms allow to move the US probe in precise and predefined ways enabling the acquisition at known spatial positions of 2D images, which can be merged together to obtain 3D information over a larger workspace with respect to commercially available 3D US probes. This feature led to the development of Robotic US (RUS) platforms performing, for example, 3D vascular reconstruction from planar US images [5-8]. However, clinical US-guided intravascular catheters manipulation is still hampered by US low resolution and poor contrast, impeding clear detection of the small-scale devices.

In this paper we demonstrate how robotics and machine learning (ML) combination can help in carrying out a complete US-based intravascular procedure (Fig. 1). A robotic

arm is exploited to permit 3D bifurcated vessel anatomical reconstruction and 3D catheter tracking and control based on standard 2D US images. On the other hand, ML methods empower precise vascular segmentation and catheter tracking while being robust to US imaging artifacts.

II. PLATFORM OVERVIEW AND MACHINE LEARNING METHODS

The proposed RUS platform is characterized by three major hardware components: a 6 degrees-of-freedom robotic arm holding both a linear US probe and a permanent magnet for catheter control, rigidly connected. The robotic procedure starts with a robotic workspace scan acquiring a sequence of US images used for precise 3D vascular reconstruction thanks to deep learning segmentation. The estimated vessel tree represents a patient specific anatomical model providing valuable help for improved diagnosis and procedure planning. During the procedure the robotic arm remotely actuates a small-scale catheter embedding a permanent magnet on the tip to navigate a bifurcated vascular structure. A ML-based tracking strategy allows to supervise the automatic catheter insertion. Detailed descriptions of these components, the US-compatible vascular phantom and the envisioned steps for a robotic medical procedure are reported in [9].

Fig. 1. Overview of the robotic platform for automatic ultrasound-guided magnetic catheter insertion. The cooperation between robotics and Machine Learning is the key-point to overcome ultrasound imaging limitations and achieve magnetic catheter automatic control. A bifurcated vessel with plaque (in yellow) and a catheter with a small magnet (in blue and grey, respectively) are shown.

A. 3D vascular reconstruction

A fundamental point for vascular reconstruction is the development of a precise vessel segmentation method. Here we considered a convolutional neural network built by modifying U-Net via VGG16 encoder integration. The network was trained through Dice loss thanks to a phantom images dataset [9]. This allowed the identification of salient image regions related to the target anatomy. Thus, the robotic arm is controlled to follow a linear trajectory over the workspace enabling the acquisition of a sequence of US images at precise spatial positions. The probe pose information given by the robot at each image acquisition step i enabled to derive the relative transformation matrices T_i . These are used to map the 2D images into the initial local US reference frame and reconstruct the 3D anatomy.

B. Catheter tracking and navigation

Automatic catheter insertion relies on the ability to precisely detect catheter tip presence inside the US images with a high reliability. To this end, a custom ML-based tracking routine has been developed. Template matching is considered to define a Region Of Interest (ROI) for catheter tip detection. This is used to reduce the whole image to a smaller portion eligible to contain catheter tip. The presence of the catheter is further assessed by a logistic regressor binary classifier, exploiting ROI statistics. The classifier is trained via gradient descent thanks to a dataset consisting of 500 images, half including and half without the catheter tip. This custom tracking strategy is integrated into the robotic arm control loop thanks to a Variable Structure Binary Feedback Control. The robotic arm drives the catheter inside the vascular structure by exploiting its magnetic interactions with the external permanent magnet and at each time step an image is acquired to check for correct manipulation. The output of the classifier is used to decide whether to continue insertion or to halt the procedure.

III. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION & RESULTS

3D vascular reconstruction is evaluated computing a distance map between the US-reconstructed anatomy and a CAD reference model. The two corresponding point clouds are aligned by Iterative Point Cloud (IPC) registration and Euclidean distance between each point is derived. The median reconstruction error is 0.95 mm with an interquartile range of 1.04 mm. An example of CNN vessel segmentation is reported in Fig. 2a, while Fig. 2b illustrates thereconstruction error map.

Automatic catheter driving is assessed considering both ML-based tracking performances, in terms of sensitivity and specificity, and control error. Classifier sensitivity and specificity turn out to be both equal to 98%, and examples of correctly classified images are reported in Fig. 2c. The control error, defined as the distance between catheter tip and anatomical target as vessel stenosis, is 3.3 mm.

IV. DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION

This article describes a novel ML-based RUS platform for intravascular catheter procedures with promising results in terms of 3D anatomical reconstruction and magnetic catheter

manipulation inside vascular bifurcations. A bifurcated vascular structure has been reconstructed with sub-millimetric precision from a sequence of US images. Additionally, Variable Structure Binary Feedback Control based on ML feedback has been validated for catheter manipulation achieving millimetric control error.

Here we show how robotics and ML can compensate for the two major drawbacks of US imaging, as its limited field of view and difficult interpretability. The development of such research methods can boost the adoption of US imaging to the detriment of computed tomography, which exposes patients and surgeons to ionizing radiations.

Fig. 2. ML-based results. A. performances of VGG-Unet in vascular segmentation from US-images. Scale bar 4 mm. b. Reconstruction distance map. c. Examples of the ML-based catheter tracking frames. Scale bar 8 mm.

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